

THE IMPACT OF REGULAR PHYSICAL ACTIVITY ON THE OVERALL HEALTH OF SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract. *The given article examines the impact of regular physical activity on the overall health of school-aged children. A comparative analysis was conducted involving 827 schoolchildren, some of whom regularly participated in physical education and sports, while others led predominantly sedentary lifestyles. Data from in-depth medical examinations conducted between 2018 and 2021 were utilized. The results show that regular sports activities contribute to improved health, increased immune resilience, and a higher proportion of practically healthy children. The findings underscore the importance of integrating physical activity into the daily lives of schoolchildren.*

Keywords: *schoolchildren, physical activity, sports, children's health, medical examinations, disease prevention.*

Introduction. One of the most accessible and effective ways to prevent health issues is the regular involvement of children in sports and physical education activities [3,5]. Regular physical activity promotes harmonious physical development, improves the functioning of the cardiovascular, respiratory, and musculoskeletal systems, strengthens immunity, and develops self-regulation skills and endurance. Additionally, sports play an important role in the psycho-emotional development of children: they reduce anxiety levels, contribute to the development of self-confidence, improve mood, and foster socialization within a group [1,7].

Definitely, school age is a period of intense physical, mental, and personal development, during which the foundations of a healthy lifestyle are laid, as well as value orientations and behavioral patterns [2,3]. Therefore, forming a well-rounded personality in schoolchildren through physical education represents an important pedagogical and social task [6].

The study of the impact of sports on the health of schoolchildren is particularly relevant in today's conditions and requires a comprehensive scientific approach, incorporating medical-biological, pedagogical, and psychological research methods [4,8]. The data obtained could serve as a basis for developing effective physical education programs aimed at improving the quality of life and health of the younger generation.

Research Objective. To assess the impact of regular physical activity on the general health of school-aged children based on the data from in-depth medical examinations.

Materials and Methods. The study included 827 schoolchildren from different schools in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. All the children were conditionally divided into two groups: the first group consisted of children who regularly engaged in sports and physical activities (including school physical education classes, sports clubs, and sections), while the second group consisted of children with low physical activity levels. Health assessments were conducted based on data from in-depth medical examinations from 2018, 2019, 2020, and 2021. The key criterion for assessment

was the classification by health groups: Group I — virtually healthy, Groups II and III with functional deviations or chronic diseases.

A control was also carried out to ensure that the structure and content of each physical education lesson corresponded to the curriculum, taking into account the students' age, health status, and physical fitness levels.

Research Results. It has been scientifically proven that only by understanding the patterns of the physical education process can we regulate comprehensive and harmonious physical development.

During the study, data from in-depth medical examinations of 827 schoolchildren aged 7 to 17 years old living in the Republic of Karakalpakstan were analyzed. The children were divided into two groups: the first group consisted of schoolchildren who regularly engaged in physical education and sports, while the second group consisted of those who did not participate in extracurricular sports activities.

One of the conditions for proper physical education in schools is well-organized medical supervision. Its tasks include the wide use of fundamental physical education tools and methods to strengthen children's health, as well as controlling their correct application, and creating appropriate conditions for physical education work. To carry out these tasks, a school-attached doctor conducts medical examinations of students to assess their health and physical development, systematically monitors physical exercise sessions and the sanitary-hygienic condition of the places where they take place, conducts health education among students, parents, and teachers, and participates in the development and implementation of school programs to improve children's health and prevent injuries.

The results showed that the general health status was significantly higher among children who engaged in regular physical activity. This group had a higher proportion of students categorized in the I health group (virtually healthy children). From 2018 to 2021, the proportion of children in this group increased: in 2018 — 37.9%, in 2019 — 46.9%, in 2020 — 47.0%, and in 2021 — 47.3%. Figure 1.

**The change in the percentage of practically healthy children (group I health)*

Figure 1. Proportion of virtually healthy children engaged in regular sports activities

This indicates a stable positive trend and the effectiveness of the implemented health improvement measures, including mandatory physical education lessons, sectional training, and active forms of leisure.

In contrast, among children who were not involved in systematic physical activities, there was a higher number of students with chronic diseases of the respiratory, cardiovascular, and musculoskeletal systems. They more frequently reported complaints of fatigue, weakness, loss of appetite, and sleep disturbances. Additionally, their level of physical endurance and indicators of cardiovascular functional status (heart rate, blood pressure at rest and after exercise) were significantly lower compared to the active group.

Data analysis also revealed a positive effect of sports on the psycho-emotional state of children. Schoolchildren who participated in physical education and sports exhibited a higher level of self-esteem, self-confidence, better socialization, and communication skills. They showed fewer signs of anxiety and emotional instability.

Certainly, for achieving harmonious development, a comprehensive approach is important. This should involve not only scheduled classes but also the creation of a motivating educational environment, incorporating knowledge about health, proper nutrition, hygiene, and the prevention of harmful habits into the curriculum.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that physical education is a crucial tool for the harmonious development of schoolchildren, positively influencing not only physical health but also intellectual and emotional well-being. The formation of a well-rounded personality in a student is impossible without a systematic organization of physical education. Physical culture in the school environment serves not only a health-improving function but also plays a key role in the development of the child's personal and social qualities. A comprehensive approach to physical education, considering the age, psychological, and individual characteristics of students, allows for the creation of conditions for full development, health enhancement, increased academic motivation, and social adaptation of children. A promising direction is the introduction of programs aimed at integrating physical education into the overall development of a person and the formation of a health culture as the foundation for a successful and active life.

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